

Small towns in the metropolitan age: an introduction

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Abstract

In urban studies, the situation of small towns and their characteristic structures, and interdependencies are overshadowed by the much-discussed growth of very large cities. When analysing the development of metropolitan regions, we advocate taking effective account of smaller urban centres, and not just the largest ones. As an introduction to this special issue, this paper wishes to place small towns in recent debates about planning and governance of metropolitan regions. We explore three themes: functional relations and socio-spatial dynamics, spatial imaginaries and narratives, and the role of small towns in the governance of metropolitan regions. We then present a brief overview of the articles included in this special issue on small towns in the metropolitan age.

Keywords

Small towns, metropolitan regions, urban studies, functional relations, narratives, governance

Introduction

Analysing the spatial dimension of the development of human societies has a long history. As early as the 1950s, the French economist François Perroux formulated his theory of growth poles: “It is a fact that growth and development are associated with territorial agglomeration and the densification of investments, people, exchanges and information at specific points” (Perroux, 1981: 181). Despite the alternative theories advocating bottom-up approaches to regional development that later emerged (Stöhr & Tödtling, 1977; Coffey & Polèse, 1985), polarisation remains a major phenomenon for many scholars. All over the world, large cities, metropolitan regions and megaregions have been seen for decades as major places of a society based on knowledge, innovation and creativity (Sassen, 1991; Scott, 2001; Ross, 2009).¹

¹ In Europe, Dijkstra et al. (2013) argue that the relationship between the city size and their economic performance has a limited relevance. Indeed, if one observes the 264 metropolitan areas in the OECD countries that have a size of over 500,000 inhabitants, those located in Europe represent only 36% of the total population and 43% of the total GDP. In North America, metropolitan areas represent 53% of the total population and 58% of the total GDP, while in Asia, 69% of the total population and 70% of the total GDP (OECD, 2012). In the most developed EU countries (EU-15), the conurbations with a

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However, many urban and regional planning researchers insist on the spatial nature of metropolitan development and they put forward four series of arguments. First, these growth centres are not islands. Competing on a global scale on specific features, metropolitan regions also form destinations linked together by major communication routes, in the form of corridors that are often impervious to exchanges with the areas they cross (Fau et al., 2014; Rodrigue, 2017).

Secondly, fostering innovation and attracting the ‘creative class’ seem to require the ongoing regeneration of central or pericentral areas of metropolitan cores. These projects involve renovating and converting old industrial buildings for other uses, and creating new emblematic buildings designed by renowned architects, while increasing the role of nature in the city (Gustedt et al., 2022; Demazière & Leducq, forthcoming). This transformation of urban spaces is not without social consequences. For instance, Krueger and Savage (2007) argue that, “as cities and city-regions develop and redevelop urban cores, lower paid support workers, and former residents of these communities, suffer. Sustainability policies (e.g. protection of green belt, growth controls) here may price low-wage earners out of local housing markets leading to long-distance commuting, two-income households and negative impacts in terms of environmental pollution, and low quality of family and community life” (Krueger & Savage, 2007: 217-218).

Thirdly, some scholars such as Kunzmann (2004), Wheeler (2009) and Westerink et al. (2013) have shown that the spatial expansion of large conurbations conflicts with the principles of sustainable development. Immoderate land consumption has a direct impact on ecosystems, while the increase in commuter traffic degrades air quality and raises noise levels (Westerink et al., 2013). Today, a new context with global dimensions (climate change, depletion of fossil fuels and minerals, etc.) is imposing itself on the local authorities responsible for managing cities and regions. In metropolitan regions undergoing economic, demographic and spatial growth, how can we control the impact on the environment, while also promoting social and territorial cohesion?

Finally, whilst metropolisation is asserting the constitution of meso-economic spaces to replace the nation state (Scott, 2001), a strand of urban planning research has questioned the scale of the metropolitan region in terms of the possibility of devising new forms of spatial planning (Albrechts et al., 2017; Zimmermann et al., 2020). These studies raise the following question: what is the capacity of stakeholders in metropolitan regions to build a common project, and therefore to participate in defining its spatial translation through planning documents?

Where can we place small towns in this vast debate on the functioning, planning and governance of metropolitan regions? This is the initial question underlying this issue of the

population of over 250,000 inhabitants, have increased their share in the GDP of only 0.6% in the 2000s (Dijkstra et al, 2013). All this suggests that urbanisation based on large cities is not the key element of economic growth in Europe.

European Journal of Spatial Development which, due to the large number of papers that we received, takes the form of two subsequent volumes. To begin with, it should be emphasised that the dynamic expansion of metropolitan regions is not limited to processes of diffusion of certain economic or residential functions, but also includes polarisation phenomena (Lichter et al., 2020; Meijers & Cardoso, 2021). New polarities are emerging or re-emerging in metropolitan areas, most often as a result of the grafting onto an old urban or village network of habits generated by new ways of living, working, travelling and meeting people from the large cities. Small towns and rural areas are then redefined spatially as they grow in population size and become integrated into the social fabric and economic life of the metropolitan region (Lichter et al., 2020).

A decade ago, a publication from the EU Commission showed that only 30 percent live in cities with more than 100,000 inhabitants, while 38 percent of the EU population live in conurbations with 5,000 to 100,000 inhabitants (European Commission, 2011). The latter urban type was loosely called ‘small and medium-sized towns’. A few years later, in their ESPON study, Servillo et al. (2014) identified 8,314 small and medium-sized towns with between 5,000 and 50,000 people across Europe, with a total population of 109 million inhabitants in 2011 (21.6% of the total population). They showed that services of general interest are typically located in small towns and argued that small and medium-sized towns may have a strategic importance in terms of territorial cohesion. Over and above the debates on population thresholds and the functions that characterise small towns, there is a clear need to study these places in order to understand the issues they face (ARL, 2019).

Even in countries having many very dynamic cities, ‘small places’ still cover a large part of the national territory, together with rural areas. This aspect matters when considering current challenges faced by European society, such as the loss of biodiversity, air pollution, climate change, and so on. Against this background, should small towns be considered as green paradises, as compared to large cities? Can nature become a defining and central aspect of urban life in a small town and important to its identity (Beatley, 2022)? This is not that simple since, in many countries, small towns currently find themselves in an uncertain position, as metropolisation, urban growth and the dynamic development of urban regions impact their position in urban systems and their functions (Bański, 2021; Meijers & Cardoso, 2021).

We proposed this special issue for several reasons. First, even though there has been a rise in the number of publications devoted to small and medium-sized towns in the last two decades, this cannot compare with the gigantic number of papers and books published each year on ‘global cities’, ‘world cities’ or ‘megacities’ (Bell & Jayne, 2009; Grove & Wagner, 2021). In urban studies, “the situation of small towns and their characteristic structures, interdependencies and trends are overshadowed by the much-discussed growth of large cities” (ARL, 2019: 4). When analysing the development of metropolitan regions, we advocate taking

effective account of smaller centres, and not just the largest ones. Second, when examining research devoted to small towns, we find that a large number of studies deal with “autonomous towns” to use the vocabulary of the first ESPON study dedicated to this subject (ÖIR, 2006). In the media and among decision-makers, this sometimes leads to gloomy representations of small towns. However, many small towns contradict this cliché: they are not suffering demographic decline, job losses or a reduction in the presence of services of general interest (Servillo et al., 2014).

This special issue focuses on small towns that are affected by metropolisation and the dynamic development of urban regions. We would like to examine the planning challenges posed by this specific spatial situation. We feel that such towns can represent fascinating cases for planning practice and research. They push us to think about regional urban systems, instead of treating categories of urban places ranked according to their weight in population or in jobs. Across Europe, very few studies have been devoted to the situation or role of small towns in larger metropolitan areas (for the US, see Lichter et al., 2020). Among the exceptions, we may quote the study by Adam (2006) which was devoted to medium-sized towns (20,000 to 100,000 inhabitants) in functional urban regions in Germany, thus overlooking the case of smaller urban settlements. In Spain, Garmendia et al. (2008) examined residential development in “small cities” that are integrated in metropolitan areas by high-speed train. They showed that the high-speed train helps isolated cities to acquire territorial roles of greater importance. In Switzerland, Kaufmann and Meili (2019) studied four small or medium-sized towns within the metropolitan region of Zurich. They analysed the impact of local policies on the economic specialisation of these towns. In spite of all these illuminating papers, we also observe that very little analysis has been carried out on how territorial cooperation could bring reciprocal benefits or challenges between metropolitan cores and smaller urban poles.

What could be the future of small towns in (or near) metro regions? On the one hand, they might attract more and more households that currently live in very large cities and become fully-fledged service centres serving the needs of their inhabitants, instead of functioning only as dormitory towns (Demazière, 2022). This rosy view has been fuelled by the COVID-19 pandemic, which has led to significant migration from metropolitan to non-metropolitan areas in some European countries (Mariotti et al., 2022). But is this trend going to continue in the long term? On the other hand, given the increasing concentration of skilled jobs and higher services in the core of large urban conurbations, small towns could become more dependent on large cities. This would imply that more and more residents of small satellite towns commute to big cities for work, higher education, health, shopping, etc. In the end, the functional interrelationships between small towns and large cities are becoming stronger but also increasingly hierarchical. Land pressures and socio-spatial inequalities appear, and planning regulations hardly solve these challenges (Demazière, 2022). Residents’ fears about pollution and loss of biodiversity are not confined to large cities. In small towns,

risks to water resources can generate conflict, and certain development projects can also be contested.

Giving more attention to the urban settlements that are at the bottom of urban hierarchies should certainly not mean idealising them. By describing the medium-sized town as an “unidentified real object”, Brunet (1997: 188) argued that such places are undeniably a stratum of the urban system while it is hard to define them by specific criteria. In fact, when undertaking a cross-national comparison, one is confronted with a variety of criteria for identifying small and medium-sized towns. We return to this issue in the following section.

Defining small towns and metropolitan regions

It is important at the outset to define (small) towns and metropolitan areas, without repeating the vast literature on the topic. The problem is that no uniform definitions exist and there is often confusion between administrative, morphological and functional definitions (Servillo et al., 2017). There is also a trade-off between territorial and more qualitative approaches when defining the “urban” and thus towns which sit somewhere on the continuum between the rural and the urban.

In particular territorial definitions suffer from vast differences in the structure and size of local governments (Servillo et al., 2017). Administrative units are often a poor reflection of the morphological settlement. In countries with large local administrative units, small towns are often difficult to identify as they are often one amongst many towns within the territory. Using a population threshold based on local administrative units is therefore misleading.

There are numerous definitions of towns, usually differentiating different classes based on size. Even within countries, there can be multiple definitions. In the UK, the lower thresholds are defined by the Office for National Statistics as 5,000, 20,000 and 75,000 for small, medium and large towns respectively, while 225,000 marks the boundary between a town and a city, though this means that many ceremonial cities below that threshold are statistically treated as towns. However, a parliamentary briefing paper (Baker, 2018) uses 7,500, 25,000 and 60,000, for small, medium and large towns respectively and 175,000 as the town/city distinction, which in itself was an amended classification of the now abolished Centre for Towns using yet again different thresholds (Centre for Towns, 2017).

The definition of the ESPON TOWN project sets a population threshold of 5,000, 25,000 and 50,000 for small, medium and large towns respectively with a minimum population density of 300 inhabitants per square kilometre (Russo et al., 2017). It has become a reference point since, although researchers still rely on national classifications (e.g. Wolff et al., 2021). The boundaries between different town classes are ultimately somewhat arbitrary.

The focus of the special issue is on small towns in or nearby metropolitan areas and therefore the defining metropolitan areas is important. In an attempt to harmonise approaches, the OECD (2012) together with the European Commission developed a

standardised definition of functional urban areas that has since been applied. Metropolitan regions refer to functional urban areas with a total population of 500,000 and higher. The OECD definition clearly relates to functional aspects of urban integration, chiefly commuting, and thus explicitly ignores administrative definitions. Nevertheless, the definition relies on local administrative units as geographic building blocks, making the approach less precise in countries with large local administrative units – a problem that is recognised but difficult to address (see also Dijkstra et al., 2019).

The functional integration, however, is only one dimension. Of equal importance is the political dimension. Metropolitan institutions have received renewed attention in the 1990s with the rise of the competitiveness agenda (Brenner, 2003). Since then, new forms of territorial cooperation have emerged, though with vast differences in terms of degrees of institutionalisation, territorial scale and powers (Demazière, 2021; Zimmermann et al., 2020).

In the articles of this special issue, we generally follow the ESPON TOWN definition, although slight variations may exist due to the use of existing datasets. Ultimately, some ambiguity will remain. The relationship with metropolitan areas is taking into account both functional and administrative approaches. In particular the latter is critical, as it has repercussions for the political representation of small towns.

Small towns in metro regions: three avenues for research

Aiming to develop a transnational and interdisciplinary approach to the chosen subject, the articles gathered here deal with a wide range of research questions in various national or transnational contexts. They are organised into three themes, which we explore below.

Functional relations and socio-spatial dynamics

Within urban research, the role of small and medium-sized towns is often invisible (Bell & Jayne, 2009; ARL, 2019; Steinführer et al., 2021). In much of the economic geography literature, they are not even worth a mention and remain an invisible part of the city or city region (e.g., Scott, 2001). This is partly also due to the limited availability of data on small and medium size allowing for cross-national comparison (see Terfrüchte & Growe, 2024). Whilst there have been some recent initiatives on small and medium-sized towns in general, their specific role within metropolitan areas remains vague. So far, the literature mainly distinguishes the functional and demographic effects (e.g. Meijers & Cardoso, 2021; Volgmann et al., 2022), but most studies look at small and medium-sized towns as a single category.

One important strand of research looks at the effects of the core city on smaller places in terms of the type of functions present, both in secondary cities as well as small and medium-sized towns (Burger et al., 2015; Meijers & Cardoso, 2021). Drawing on the concept of ‘borrowed size’ by Alonso (1973) suggesting that smaller places can benefit from being in proximity to larger ones by exhibiting a wider range of functions than could be expected due

to the size of a place, others have proposed that large metropolitan areas may actually lead to a below-average presence of certain functions, indicated by the idea of ‘agglomeration shadow’ (Burger et al., 2015; Meijers & Cardoso, 2021).

In demographic terms, many studies have focused on population development in functional urban regions, distinguishing an urban core and a dependent suburban ring (e.g. Van den Berg et al., 1982; Parr, 2012). However, it is noticeable that in general the attention is on the urban core, whilst small towns are subsumed in the amorphous urban ring (Dembski et al., 2021). Equally the concept of counter-urbanisation that emerged in the 1970s and suggested that urban populations left metropolitan areas included both overspill beyond the boundaries of metropolitan regions and growth in small and medium-sized towns in rural areas (Berry, 1980).

Research suggests that much depends on the dynamics of the core city. For Germany, Volgmann et al. (2022) found that in the majority of cities that show at least population or employment growth above the national average, their hinterlands tend to benefit through demographic and employment growth above the national average, though the study does not take into account regional effects. In terms of demographic change, a study by Dembski et al. (2021) found that more prosperous city regions were likely to show widespread population growth. In a similar vein, Humer et al. (2022) found that in the Netherlands, population growth in polycentric urban regions to be increasingly synchronised between core and ring due to the functional integration.

More research is needed to better understand the functional and demographic dynamics in small and medium-sized towns in relation to metropolitan areas, which too often are ‘rest’ categories in urban research. There is a need to better understand how being part of a metropolitan area shapes small and medium-sized towns and how they shape the metropolitan area.

Narratives and imaginaries

In many European countries, a significant proportion of inhabitants actually live in small and medium-sized towns (Servillo et al., 2014). Yet, their residential experience is structurally ignored, as urban studies focus on cities and metropolises (Steinführer, 2016). Since its origin, urban studies have been dominated by the analytical frameworks of research on large cities in developed countries (Bell & Jayne, 2009; Robinson, 2002). In Europe, London and Paris have been the subjects of analyses too numerous to be listed. In North America, the city of Chicago gave rise to the establishment of an eponymous school of sociological thought in the early twentieth century. In contrast, memorable sociological studies on small-sized cities are much less numerous. We can cite *Middletown: A Study in American Culture*, conducted by Robert and Helen Lynd (1929) on the town of Muncie (30,000 inhabitants), about a 60-mile drive

from Indianapolis. In this work, now a classic of sociology, the authors applied methods of cultural anthropology for the first time to the study of a Western town.

Even though small towns in various geographical contexts may share more similarities than differences, the lack of available statistical data makes it hard to grasp cultural variations (ARL, 2019), and misinterpretation of observed phenomenon may create obstacles towards a high-quality cross-country comparative analysis of small towns development. In the last decades, a significant part of academic research on small towns has tended to focus on negative narratives (Hannemann, 2004; Bidou-Zachariasen & Authier, 2017) for instance in the context of population decline, urban shrinkage, deindustrialization or brain drain (Roquès, 2009; Gribat et al., 2022). Other research on spatial narratives and imaginaries of small towns may evoke a sense of nostalgia, community, and intimacy (Gunko & Medvedev, 2018). The narrative about small towns may also combine simplicity, close social ties, short distance, easy access to the economic or political decision makers. However, does the smallness of a place foster sociability and encourage community life and exchanges? Reality challenges these images, with many social relations being influenced by commuting to another town or to a large city for work, study or leisure.

Landscape seems to be crucial to the small town's identity (Beatley, 2022). Many narratives are shaped by the physical layout of the small town, its interrelation with natural surroundings (rivers, mountains, forests, etc.), its architecture related to historical context and collective memory, landmarks as a churches, squares or trees serving as point of reference of the local identity, and the interactions of its inhabitants (Gribat et al., 2022). Small towns are also seen as easy to get to grips with: they can be quickly circumnavigated. Their urban structure around market halls or facilities, often located in the heart of a heritage-laden old town centre, is easy to understand, even if these towns are tending to experience the effects of suburbanisation and urban sprawl (Taulelle, 2010). Obviously, these images are clichés, mental representations that make up a city model. But we can also add other, very different clichés: lifeless towns, the dormitory towns of major metropolises, or towns that are home to large shopping centres and business parks.

In relation with the metropolitan cores – opposition, contribution or ignorance – small towns also have their own imagined futures, shaped by the hopes, dreams, and aspirations of their residents. These visions for the future influence the way the town evolves over time and contribute to its ongoing spatial narrative. The calls for developing more positive, spatial narratives of small towns have a particular resonance today. Small towns have become more popular than densely urban cores during lockdowns in the COVID-19 pandemic, in the context of the rise of digital, remote work, increasing rents and real estate prices in metropolitan areas. Are these new narratives and imaginaries likely to influence public discourse, urban development and planning practices? More research is welcome with comparative studies on

external–internal narratives of small towns located in metropolitan cores and their role in defining the position of small towns in metropolitan urban systems.

Institutions and policies

In the discussion about institutions, policy and tools that may acknowledge the role played by small towns in metropolitan development, we shall first go back to the decades-long but illuminating debate on metropolitan reform. Second, various types of metropolitan governance (voluntary, variable, more formal, etc.) exist nowadays across the European continent. The metro government may take the form of a metropolitan institution with competences and financial resources, but it may also correspond to a model of governance based on informal agreements (Tomàs, 2020). Recently there have been some attempts in several European countries to create some hard forms of metropolitan government. However, what is the possibility for small towns to negotiate their place in such institutional settings? What benefits can a small town get from being involved in some formal metropolitan government or in a city-region partnership if it stands out?

The management of metropolitan regions has been the topic of intense academic debates for over half a century (Brenner, 2009; Kantor & Savitch, 2010; Tomàs, 2020). As early as in the 1960s, the permanent gap between municipal boundaries and metropolitan areas has led scholars such as Wood (1958) to argue for one integrated government for the whole city region. In contrast, authors embracing public choice theory consider that municipalities are the right scale and that competition among them ensures greater efficiency and democracy (Ostrom et al., 1961; Tomàs, 2020). This debate is very much influenced by the US case, and we plead for more analysis in the case of European countries. This is not an easy task since the institutional systems in European countries are quite diverse, with federal, decentralised as well as centralised systems (Nadin & Stead, 2008).

In their account of the processes of building metropolitan institutions, Lefèvre and Weir (2010) contrast the dynamics in the USA and in Western Europe. In the US, “the most widespread of the new regional institutions have been networks of civic groups. These include efforts of regional chambers of commerce to promote regional economic development [and] ad hoc collections of groups from public, private and non-profit sectors that collaborate to achieve specific regional goals, such as building regional infrastructure or cleaning up the environment” (Lefèvre & Weir, 2010: 631-632). Such coalitions are seen as too focused on their goals and unable to address structural issues linked to spatial disparities related to income, or to address fiscal disparities across local governments (Wheeler, 2009).

By contrast, in many European countries (with the notable exception of Germany or Spain), the national government has played (and still plays) a key role in shaping debates about city-regions and their governance (Kantor & Savitch, 2010). In general, the rules delineating the boundaries of subnational governments, their functions and their relation to

the state were often defined in the nineteenth century (Bonnet-Pineau & Vandermotten, 2016). Since then, many reforms have taken place with various aims, like amalgamation or decentralisation, and nowadays the institutional landscape of European countries is quite dense. As a consequence, any process of creating or reforming metropolitan governments is bound to set tensions on the established distribution of power (Lefèvre, 1998; Demazière, 2021). According to the result of the political fights between diverse levels of government, the new metropolitan tier may have administrative boundaries that are a far cry from the functional urban areas that they are supposed to govern. Also, they may have (or lack) resources or political legitimacy to act on the challenges met by metropolitan regions. These aspects have been dealt with recently in research on various forms of metro governments in European countries like the Czech Republic, England, Estonia, France, Italy or Poland (see ESPON, 2021; Cotella et al., 2024; Casavola et al., 2024). Such research shows that metropolitan institutions emerge out of political struggle and within existing (national) institutional systems. In this conflict-laden context, horizontal cooperation between small town authorities and metropolitan governments may occur or not.

Obviously, the capacity to implement metropolitan public policies of public transportation, sustainability or housing is certainly higher when there are technical, human and economic resources within an institution created with this purpose. However, the attitudes of local actors towards cooperation also shape the outputs. Metropolitan institutions can be ineffective if representatives block them in the name of local autonomy. Indeed, the capacity to “think metropolitan”, that is, to overcome local interests in the name of a metropolitan common interest, is a key issue in metropolitan governance (Tomàs, 2012). Even though the national or regional government may develop schemes or incentives that facilitate cooperation between local authorities in metropolitan regions, the result is by no means guaranteed.

Whether the focus is on hard government or soft spaces the aim of this special issue on small towns in metropolitan regions is to explore several main governance questions. We ask specifically whether metropolitan governance arrangements align with the functional city-region. We also want to find out what are the advantages for a small-town authority to be included in or to cooperate with a metro government. Conversely, what are the advantages and limitations to stand alone? Regarding the metropolitan planning or development instruments, what are the ones that can promote cooperation between small towns and metropolitan authorities? Do instruments that make room for small towns exist or do so only on paper? In any case, it is certainly difficult for small municipalities to interact with metropolitan development governance, whether from within or outside metropolitan areas. To account for this difficulty, the OECD study about rural-urban partnerships may be a source of inspiration. It argues that “co-operation appears to be more difficult when the differences in size, resources and capacity between urban and rural areas are large. Other factors detrimental to effective

partnership are regulatory and political barriers, lack of trust and policy fragmentation” (OECD, 2013: 16).

Origin of the special issue

This publication emerged from research activities of the international working group “Small Towns and Metropolitan Cores: Towards Cooperation? A European Perspective”, which has been initiated and funded by the Academy for Territorial Development in the Leibniz Association (ARL). The work of ARL is carried out in an inter- and transdisciplinary setup in which experts from science and practice cooperate to provide knowledge-based analyses and advice on current issues of urban and regional development. The international working group consisted of the following members: Christophe Demazière (Chair), Université de Lille, France; Hans Thor Andersen, Aalborg University, Denmark; Jerzy Bański, Polish Academy of Science, Poland; Yane Marie Conradi, Technical University of Darmstadt, Germany; Giancarlo Cotella, Politecnico di Torino, Italy; Sebastian Dembski, University of Liverpool, United Kingdom; Maria Gunko, University of Oxford, United Kingdom; Divya Leducq, Université de Lille, France; Evert Meijers, Utrecht University, Netherlands; Sofia Morgado, Universidade de Lisboa, Portugal; Loris Servillo, Politecnico di Torino, Italy; and Evelyn Gustedt, Filip Śnieg and Sebastian Krätzig, ARL – Academy for Territorial Development in the Leibniz Association, Germany.

The aim of the working group was to analyse how small European towns face metropolitan development and its associated challenges. The ambition was set on developing a transnational and interdisciplinary approach by building on existing scientific traditions of studying small towns in various European countries. Within the working period of three years (2021–2023), the group members have been meeting multiple times (online and in presence). They also launched a call for contributions which resulted in a seminar in September 2022. Through this event, various academics could share their views on the topic of the working group. Subsequently, some of these presentations were selected in view of this special issue and the potential authors were given detailed comments, so as to help them with writing their paper. With the ideas presented in the special issue, all contributors aim at shedding new light on the importance of small towns in the development of metropolitan regions across Europe and to contribute simultaneously to ongoing scholarly debates.

Organisation of the special issue

The papers that are included in this special issue on small towns in the metropolitan age explore a broad range of research questions. They are organised along the three themes introduced above and will be spread across two volumes.

A first series of papers explores the functional interdependencies between small towns and their larger neighbouring city or cities. Thomas Terfrüchte and Anna Growe analyse

dynamics all over the European continent, while Jerzy Bański focuses on Poland, Christian Fertner, Høgni Kalsø Hansen and Lars Winther on Denmark and Madeleine Wagner on Germany. They show that what happens in small towns is often dependent on developments in larger cities, and that reciprocal relationships also exist. Such interdependencies come to the fore in different types of functional relationships (e.g. commuting, leisure trips, household and firm migration, etc.) and changing functions and socio-demographic compositions of both the smaller and the larger city. The papers present functional typologies of small towns, they show development trajectories of small towns in relation to their larger neighbour, and they illustrate various patterns of specialisation and concentration of urban functions.

Beyond functional relationships, there are multiple other kinds of relations between small towns and their neighbouring big cities. Exploring the roles of small towns and perceptions within metropolitan urban systems is a promising research avenue. These complex linkages are often reported through commonly shared narratives and spatial imaginaries. In the second volume of this special issue, two contributions are made that enrich the academic discussion on discourses on narratives and (spatial) imaginaries regarding small towns. Franziska Görmar on the one hand and Inga Bolik and Yane Conradi on the other hand develop comparative studies on external–internal narratives of small towns located in metropolitan regions, respectively in Eastern and Western Germany. They highlight interrelations between narratives or imaginaries and landscape, urban design or quality of life. They also show that the most efficacious narratives and imaginaries are likely to influence public discourse and thus urban development.

A third series of papers deal with metropolitan institutions and governance. Using the cases of England, France and Italy, Giancarlo Cotella, Christophe Demazière, Sebastian Dembski and Loris Servillo show the diversity of policy arrangements for metropolitan cooperation and the diversity of instruments (strategic planning, financial incentives for cooperation, amalgamation of local governments, etc.). In a paper devoted to Italy, Donato Casavola, Elisabetta Vitale Brovarone and Giancarlo Cotella analyse cooperation schemes between small town authorities and metropolitan governments. They analyse the political and social implications for small towns of taking part in a metropolitan institution with competences and financial resources. In the cases of Turin and Bari, they show the uneven capacity to act of metropolitan authorities in public transportation, sustainability or housing, affecting the quality of life in small towns and their access to big cities.

Acknowledgements

The Special Issue benefitted from the generous support of the Academy for Territorial Development in the Leibniz Association (ARL), which hosted the international working group “Small Towns and Metropolitan Cores: Towards Cooperation? A European Perspective” between 2021 and 2023. We would like to thank the members of the working group and the

contributors for the rich debates. We would also like to thank the referees of the individual contributions for providing valuable feedback.

Conflict of interest

The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

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